

Summer School on Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia

Description

The RDMTraining4NFDI Summer School on Research Data Management is aimed at data stewards and RDM professionals who regularly deliver discipline-specific training. To tailor the program to participants' needs, we will assess your experience level via a short survey (see on the next page), and adapt the content accordingly.

While this edition is primarily geared toward experienced practitioners, we are committed to building capacity for the future — so we will also cover key RDM fundamentals. We warmly welcome both newcomers and seasoned data stewards. Where possible, we will offer parallel sessions based on experience level or invite more advanced participants to contribute feedback and insights on foundational materials.

The aim is to:

- Assist consortia in creating courses with general core content and data-specific adaptations.
- Cover content tailored to the specific RDM needs across groups of NFDI consortia (e.g. sensitive data, qualitative data, geospatial data).
- Strengthen participants training skills through interactive, expert-led training with practical exercises and peer exchange.
- Foster cross-disciplinary collaboration and effective data sharing among consortia.
- Gather feedback to enhance our training program.

The Summer School will be developed and delivered through a collaborative effort between RDMTraining4NFDI institutions and discipline-specific use cases, with contributions from experienced external trainers.

Please register here until 2025-06-16. You may not receive a form response notification, but you will receive a follow-up email with further information (including the schedule) at the beginning of July.

Dates and Times

2025-08-18 to 2025-08-22

- Monday: 10:00–17:00
- Tuesday to Friday: 09:00–17:00

Place

SR-Marie-Curie-R413
ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences
Gleueler Strasse 60
50931 Cologne
Germany

Costs

The Summer School is free of charge. We cover travel expenses up to 200€ and provide food and drinks during the day and an optional dinner on the first evening. You will need to cover the cost of your accommodation and any other evening meals.

Recommended Hotels

- 3-star Hotel Flandrischer Hof
- 3.5-star Hotel Chelsea
- 4-star Leonardo Royal Hotel Köln - Am Stadtwald

Organizer

The following RDMTraining4NFDI institutions will take the lead in organising, moderating and potentially delivering generic RDM workshops:

- ZB MED - Information Centre for Life Sciences
- TH Köln - University of Applied Sciences

The following NFDI use cases will provide discipline-specific training through five trainers and participants each:

- BERD@NFDI - Business, economics and social sciences
- KonsortSWD - Social, behavioural, educational and economic science
- NFDI4Memory - History
- NFDI4Microbiota - Microbiota research

To broaden the skill set of participants, external trainers will be invited to deliver targeted sessions on cross-cutting soft skills such as change management and didactics.

Contact

First name, last name: name@organization.de

Registration Form

1. First and last names [Open answer]

2. Email address [Open answer]
3. Institution [Open answer]
4. NFDI consortia (select all that apply)
 - BERD@NFDI
 - KonsortSWD
 - NFDI4Memory
 - NFDI4Microbiota
 - Other
5. Research area [Open answer]
6. Career stage (select all that apply)
 - Ph.D. candidate
 - Postdoctoral researcher
 - Junior professor
 - Professor
 - Director of an institute
 - RDM professional
 - Data steward
 - Data librarian
 - Trainer
 - Developer
 - Other
7. Do you have any dietary requirements? (select all that apply)
 - Lactose intolerance
 - Gluten intolerance or sensitivity
 - Vegetarianism
 - Veganism
 - Wheat allergy
 - Nut allergy
 - Fish and seafood allergy
 - Egg allergy
 - Soy allergy
 - Other
 - None
8. Would you like to join the other participants for dinner on the evening of 18 August?
(RDMTTraining4NFDI will cover up to 30€)
 - Yes
 - No
9. Do you agree to be photographed?
 - Yes
 - No
10. I hereby expressly agree to the Data protection information Summer School on
Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia (see right below)
 - Yes

Data protection information Summer School on Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia

Registration data (name, email address) of the participants will only be collected by us for the purpose of organising the event. The purpose of this data is to confirm the registration and to enable contact with the participants. It will not be passed on to third parties. For this purpose, personal data is collected in accordance with Art. 6 GDPR para. 1 (b).

Purpose and data categories

Personal data may be collected for the preparation, realisation, follow-up and documentation of events. This data includes a maximum of:

- Master data (name, title, form of address, function, etc.)
- Contact data (postal addresses, email, telephone, etc.)
- Event information
- Contact from ZB MED

Legal basis

For the purpose of preparing and organising an event and its documentation, the above-mentioned data is processed on the basis of your binding registration (Art. 6 para. 1 lit. b GDPR). For the purpose of event follow-up, e.g. for evaluations or reference to thematically similar follow-up events and publications relevant to the event, the above-mentioned data is stored on the basis of our legitimate interest (Art. 6 para. 1 lit. f GDPR) in improving the quality of our events.

Storage period

By registering, you consent to us contacting you and storing your data for the preparation, realisation, follow-up and documentation of the event. If there is no further contact with ZB MED, the personal data will be deleted from the database after 36 months with a reasonable processing period of up to three months and in individual cases after verification. In accordance with legal requirements, event documents are stored for at least ten years.

Your rights

You have the right to access and rectify the above-mentioned data categories. You can object to the processing of data for the purpose of event follow-up at any time.

Contact

you have any questions or suggestions before or after the event, please email us at rdmtraining4nfdi-orga@lists.nfdi.de.

Survey

1. Do you need train-the-trainer workshops on basic RDM concepts?

- Yes
 - No
2. If so, at what stage of the research data lifecycle? (select all that apply)
- Plan
 - Collect
 - Process
 - Analyse
 - Preserve
 - Share
 - Reuse
3. What other generic aspects of RDM would you like to know more about? [Open answer]
4. What specific applications of RDM would you like to learn more about (e.g. PIDs for instruments or samples)? [Open answer]
5. Do you need train-the-trainer workshops on discipline-specific concepts?
- Yes
 - No
6. If so, which ones? [Open answer]
7. Could this be provided by a member of your NFDI consortium?
- Yes
 - No
8. How would you rate your programming skills in Shell, R, Python and Git? [Matrix question]
- Novice
 - Advanced beginner
 - Competent
 - Proficient
 - Expert
9. What soft skills do you think would most benefit the training you provide? (select all that apply)
- Change management
 - Community building
 - Data steward tasks and challenges
 - Didactis
 - Initiatives and trend scouting
 - Persona creation
 - Project management with Git
10. What are your biggest challenges in offering RDM training? [Open answer]
11. Are there gaps that we could fill in? [Open answer]
12. What would you like to take away from this Summer School? [Open answer]
13. Do you have any questions or comments about the Summer School? [Open answer]